

TITANIUM NANO COMPOSITES USING HYDROGENATED METHOD

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Titanium is well known for its excellent properties including light weight, high specific strength, corrosion resistance, and biocompatibility. Due to these properties, Ti and Ti alloys are widely used in aerospace, chemical, and biomedical industries. However, because of the high cost of production from ore to engineering components, the applications of these metals are limited.

One way to reduce the cost of Ti production is the use of powder metallurgy method, for example hot isostatic pressing. This technology has enabled the production of a new breed of Ti-based materials, known as Ti matrix composites (TMCs), in which interest has been growing over the past few years. Titanium boride (TiB) and titanium carbide (TiC) have been identified as candidates to improve the properties of the matrix and these reinforcements confer unique properties such as high specific strength, specific stiffness, and specific fatigue resistance [1-3].

It has also been shown that the main drawback in metal matrix composites is the lack of ductility. However, recent studies are showing that using nano-scale reinforcements can prevent this decrease of ductility in the composite [4, 5].

In order to produce low cost titanium composites, reinforced with nanoscaled TiB or TiC, an innovative powder metallurgy method has been used in this work, known as the hydrogenation-dehydrogenation method.

This method, which consists on sintering from titanium hydride (TiH₂) powder, leading to Ti final sample, was first reported by Ivasishin et al.[6]. During sintering, TiH₂ will be dehydrogenated under vacuum, exposing an activated surface and enhancing sintering at elevated temperature. This approach improves the sintering of Ti allowing

attainment of better homogeneity and a relative density up to 99%, with press to sinter approach, without any additional operation.

The present work aims to investigate the improvement that can be achieved on TMC using nanosized reinforcement and the feasibility of the hydrogenation/dehydrogenation process to obtain nano-scale TMCs, starting from Ti sponge and reinforcing nanopowders. A particular focus of the research was the hydrogenation, milling, mixing and sintering stages of the preparation of these composites.

Prior simulation has been done to determinate how the TMCs can be improved by the addition of nanoscaled composites. Simple calculations have been done, using two different models regarding the reinforcement distribution and its inter particles spacing. The two different models are illustrated on Fig.1 and on the Fig.2, the results of calculations for the composite Ti/TiC, with 40nm TiC particles show the improvement that can be achieved on such composites, regardless the model took in consideration.

The process used here, to obtain the TMCs, consists in hydrogenate the Ti sponge and reduce the particle size of the TiH₂ obtained using ball milling. Then a mix between the TiH₂ particles and the reinforcement particles, a cold compaction and finally sinter it under secondary vacuum leads to our final material. Each step of this process has been studied and therefore, is controlled. A summary of the process is shown on Fig.3

The TMCs fabricated by the above-described process, as shown of the Fig.4, might exhibit very interesting mechanical properties and be tailored for desired applications.

Fig.1 Models for the reinforcement distribution a/ the cubic model (c.m) and b/ the face-centered cubic model (f.c.c)

Fig.2 Theoretical yield strength depending on the volume fraction, considering 2 models for the inter-particle spacing of the composite Ti-TiC (40nm)

Fig.3 Summary of the hydrogenation/dehydrogenation process used in our work

Fig.4 Fracture of the Ti/10vol.%TiB sample where the dots are showing the TiB needles

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